

THE INTERPRETATION OF X-RAY STRESS MEASUREMENTS OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES USING COMPUTER MODELLING TECHNIQUES

M.R.Watts and P.J.Withers

Department of Materials Science and Metallurgy, University of Cambridge, Pembroke Street, Cambridge, CB2 3QZ, United Kingdom.

SUMMARY: In this paper the interpretation of X-ray measurements of stress based on the conventional $\sin^2\psi$ method is examined for metal matrix composites. While the biaxial assumption may be valid for macrostress distributions, its range of validity for materials such as composites which contain microstresses is not so clear. A finite element model has been constructed to simulate the relaxation of an internal thermal microstress distribution near the free surface. Analytical modelling has then been used to simulate the stress distribution, on the basis of which $\sin^2\psi$ plots have been produced. This work suggests that the biaxial stress assumption is valid over a shorter region than previously thought and that this has serious implications for the interpretation of X-ray measurements made on composites. These implications are examined for an Al/SiC metal matrix particulate composite system.

KEYWORDS: residual stresses, metal matrix composites, x-rays, finite element modelling, internal stresses, thermal stresses

INTRODUCTION

The fact that the normal stress across a free surface must be zero has long been exploited for the interpretation of X-ray stress measurements using the $\sin^2\psi$ method [1-3]. Of course this assumption is only strictly true at the surface, but since the penetration of X-ray radiation within metallic materials is limited to depths of only tens of microns, in many cases it is a fair assumption for the whole of the sampling volume. While this assumption may well have merit for single phase materials, the situation is not so clear for composites, which often contain microstresses between the phases, arising for example, from differences in thermal expansion coefficient, or from plastic deformation of the matrix phase. Previously, Nishioka et al. and Hanabusa et al. [4,5] attempted to calculate the rate at which the internal stresses fall off as the free surface is approached for a regular array of second phase particles. In this paper we use finite element modelling techniques to examine the rate of decay of the stress state near-surface for a randomly distributed reinforcing phase.

When the penetration depth is significantly less than the particle spacing a steep gradient is predicted indicative of a biaxial stress and when the penetration is greater than the particle

spacing, the gradient is shallow, indicative of the hydrostatic stress state typical of the bulk. Hanabusa et al. [5] found that using their model the $\sin^2\psi$ gradient is dependent upon the depth of penetration as a fraction of the particle spacing. Traditionally, it is assumed that if the $\sin^2\psi$ plot gives a straight line then the biaxial assumption is valid, because were the biaxial assumption to be invalid one would expect to find curvature of the $\sin^2\psi$ plot arising from the decreasing depth of penetration as the ψ angle increases. In practice it is extremely rare to obtain a perfect straight line. Loss of linearity is not uncommon for MMC's and is often ascribed to poor counting statistics. However, if the effect is caused through a breakdown in the biaxial assumption, then the stress state will be very poorly estimated. In this paper the severity of this problem is investigated by modelling the stress relaxation profile from the surface for a series of composites, and to use the profiles thus deduced to simulate the associated X-ray $\sin^2\psi$ profiles. As the results amply demonstrate, for Al based composites, the estimated microstresses can be seriously in error.

EXPERIMENTAL APPROACH

The $\sin^2\psi$ Method

In general X-ray stress measurements are made using the standard $\sin^2\psi$ method (Fig.1).

Figure 1: Schematic representations illustrating the variation in d with measurement angle ψ [1].

It can be shown that [1],

$$\varepsilon_\psi - \varepsilon_y = \frac{\sigma_\phi}{E} (1 + \nu) \sin^2 \psi \quad (1)$$

where ε_ψ is the strain at an angle ψ , and ε_y is the normal strain. This equation is the basis for the $\sin^2\psi$ method for the measurement of stress using X-rays. By rewriting Eqn 1 in terms of lattice parameter instead of strains, the following equation can be arrived at;

$$\sigma_\phi = \frac{E}{(1 + \nu) \sin^2 \psi} \left(\frac{d_i - d_n}{d_n} \right) \quad (2)$$

Using this equation, it is possible to calculate in-plane stresses without having to know the unstressed plane spacing, d_o since it is assumed that the error between d_o , d_i and d_n is small.

The Finite Element Model

To simulate experimental $\sin^2\psi$ plots, two types of computer model were used. The first, a finite element model, was used to model the composite in order to calculate the extent of relaxation of the microstress profile as a function of distance from the free surface. The second was used to calculate the X-ray $\sin^2\psi$ response that such stress variation would produce.

A 25,000 element model was constructed within ABAQUS™. To reduce computational complexity a two dimensional generalised plane strain model was employed. In effect this is equivalent to studying a randomly distributed array of fibres with their axes all lying parallel to the z-axis. Each particle was represented as a square comprising 5x5 square four noded elements. Overall, the model comprised 500 elements in the x-direction and 50 element layers in the y-direction (Fig. 2). The boundaries of the model were constrained to remain planar, except for the free surface at $y=0$, across which there was no constraint at all. The x-co-ordinate of each particle was chosen at random, but ensuring that no particles were touching. With respect to the through thickness (y) co-ordinate, the particles were placed such that each layer contained the same volume fraction of particles as the composite as a whole. This procedure was chosen to simulate a random particle distribution without the need for thousands of particles to overcome the fluctuations in the stress profile from sub-surface layer to layer arising from random fluctuations in the *number* of particles in each layer. Particle volume fractions of 5, 10 and 20% were studied simply by adding more and more particles using the above procedure. The use of square particles does lead to some level of stress concentration at particle corners not present if spheres were used, but this geometry has the advantage that it requires relatively few elements to capture the geometry and it simplifies the process of calculating the average phase stresses as a function of distance from the free surface. In order to generate sizeable thermal expansion misfit microstresses, a temperature drop of 400°C was applied across the whole composite, and it was assumed that there were no temperature gradients through the body of the material. Perfect elasticity and perfect bonding across the interface of the particle/matrix were also assumed. The particle and matrix regions were assigned material properties appropriate to silicon carbide and an aluminium alloy respectively (Table 1).

Once the stress field had been computed the stress profile with distance from the free surface was calculated by measuring the average phase stress in each layer. By doing this as a function of depth from the surface, it was possible to obtain a profile of the stress as it increased from the surface into the bulk of the material. Profiles such as those shown in Fig. 3 were produced for the stress in the x, y, and z-directions, as a function of depth (y) from the free surface.

Table 1: Material properties used in finite element modelling.

Material Property	Matrix (Aluminium, 2024)	Particles (Silicon Carbide)
Young's Modulus, E (GPa)	69	400
Poisson's Ratio, ν	0.34	0.17
CTE, α (10^{-6} K^{-1})	24	4.5

Figure 2: The stress distribution caused by cooling the composite by 400°C in a small part of the FE model.

Mathematica Simulation of X-ray $\text{Sin}^2\psi$ Curves

With the stress profile for the matrix and reinforcement phases calculated it is necessary to simulate the $\text{sin}^2\psi$ curves taking into account increasing attenuation with increasing depth. The elastic strain $\epsilon(y)$ in the direction ψ at a depth y can be calculated from the stress profiles, $\sigma_x(y)$, $\sigma_y(y)$ and $\sigma_z(y)$. For a given measurement direction ψ , the strain from each layer contributes to the overall diffraction peak according to:

$$\langle \epsilon_{\psi} \rangle = \frac{\int_0^{\infty} dI_D \cdot \epsilon}{\int_0^{\infty} dI_D} \quad \text{where} \quad dI_D = \frac{I_0 ab}{\sin(\theta + \psi)} \exp \left[-\mu y \left(\frac{1}{\sin(\theta + \psi)} + \frac{1}{\sin(\theta - \psi)} \right) \right] dy \quad (3)$$

where I_0 is the incident beam intensity, and a and b are constants. By using at least five ψ angles a plot of the strain versus $\text{sin}^2\psi$ can be obtained, which can then be compared to actual experimental plots.

RESULTS

Stress Relaxation Profiles

Fig. 3a-d shows the stress profiles obtained from finite element (FEA) models of the type shown in Fig. 2. As expected, and predicted by Hanabusa et al. [5], the stress components increase from the surface towards the bulk. As required of a free surface, the out-of-plane stress, σ_y , tends to zero as the surface is approached, as do the in-plane stresses. As one might expect, little change is observed the fibre direction.

Table 2: A comparison of residual stress levels predicted from Eshelby's method and FEM models. All the values quoted are in MPa.

Direction x and y	ESHELBY		FEM	
	Matrix	Fibre	Matrix	Fibre
5%	21.7	-415.0	22.2	-434
10%	44.0	-398.0	45.5	-409
20%	89.0	-360.0	90.8	-363
z				
5%	130.0	-2520	119	-2263
10%	232.0	-2080	206	-1847
20%	366.0	-1500	329	-1318

Figure 3a-d: The stress variation with distance from the free surface within the matrix and reinforcement, for 5, 10, and 20% reinforcement.

Far from the free surface, the results of the FEA are in very good agreement with the stresses predicted by a simple Eshelby analysis (see Table 2). Because the ‘fibre’ direction is not representative of particulate composites, the following discussion will focus primarily on changes in the x and y directions. A number of features should be noted; i) as the percentage of reinforcement increases, the stresses in the matrix increase greatly, while the stresses in the particles decrease slightly. ii) The stress reaches the bulk value more quickly in the in-plane direction (x) than in the out-of-plane direction. iii) While the rate at which the bulk value is reached is dependent on the particle spacing and volume fraction, it is more closely related to the particle size in that the rise in stress is almost identical for each reinforcement fraction.

DISCUSSION

The approach of Hanabusa et al. [5] predict the following responses for the 2D and 3D cases:

$$\sigma_y(y) = A(1 + ky)\exp(-ky)\cos ky \quad (4a)$$

$$\sigma_x(y) = A(1 - ky)\exp(-ky)\cos ky \quad (4b)$$

$$\sigma_{yy}(y) = A(1 + ky)\exp(-ky)\cos ky \cos kz \quad (5a)$$

$$\sigma_x(y) = \frac{A}{2} \left(1 + 2\nu - 2\sqrt{2} \frac{\pi y}{a} \right) \exp(-\sqrt{2}ky)\cos ky \cos kz \quad (5b)$$

with $k=2\pi/a$.

While the stress profiles are in qualitative agreement with the response predicted by Hanabusa et al. [5] for the two dimensional ‘particle’ (fibre) system, Fig. 4 shows that the stress field for the random array relaxes to zero at the surface over a much shorter distance. Furthermore, the observation that the $\sigma_x(y)$ and the $\sigma_y(y)$ stress components increase at approximately the same rate with depth irrespective of particle volume fraction (see Fig. 3) is in contrast to the predictions of Hanabusa et al. [5]. This is clear from the normalised plots (Fig. 5) which do not all fall onto a single curve as Eqns 4a and b would suggest they should.

Figure 4: Predicted and experimental normalised ‘particle’ (fibre) stress profiles in the x and y -directions. The unconnected points correspond to the FE predictions of Fig. 3, and the symbols denoting the curves are the same as used in Fig. 3, 5% (open circles), 10% (closed circles), and 20% (open diamonds). Hanabusa’s model is represented by solid triangles, and the representative area 5% area fraction curves denoted by solid squares.

The difference stems from the form of the stress field fluctuation assumed by Hanabusa et al. [5] in their theoretical treatment. Essentially, the approach is too simplistic to capture this effect in that it places a row of fibres at the surface and assumes the variation in normal stress to be sinusoidal prior to cutting the free surface. It is then, this sinusoidal variation which is reduced to zero when the free surface is formed. Consequently, the model for stress relaxation contains no information about the particle size or volume fraction. In reality the stress does not decay as a sine wave from the centre of each particle, instead the stress is found to be fairly uniform within the particle and changes rapidly within the matrix (Fig.2). Eshelby’s approach is consistent with Lamé’s relationship for the out-of-plane (hoop) stress, namely that it varies as $-P(r_0/r)^3$ away from each particle where r_0 is the particle diameter [6].

In an attempt to capture these aspects of the stress distribution we have extended the approach of Hanabusa et al. [5] whilst retaining a fairly simple analytical approach. We have approximated the stress variation as a step function, having the constant value P throughout each particle $|x| < r$, as predicted by the Eshelby formulation [6], and a constant value, $-P(1-f_a)/f_a$ throughout the matrix $r_0 < |x| < a/2$ where f_a is the area fraction across the cut surface. Whilst this oversimplifies the variation of stress within the matrix, it is a good approximation when f_a is small, and will provide the opposite bound to that provided by Hanabusa et al. [5]. This variation retains the advantage of being fairly simple to describe as a Fourier series. As a result the balancing force which must be applied at $y=0$ when the free surface is introduced is given by:

$$F_y = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} A_n \sin(k_n x) \quad \text{and} \quad F_y = \sum_{n,m=1}^{\infty} A_n A_m \sin(k_n x) \sin(k_m z) \quad (6a \text{ and } b)$$

for fibres and particles respectively, with $A_n = A_0 (\sin(k_n r_0))/n$ and $k_n = 2\pi n/a$.

Figure 5: Normalised plots of the FE derived stress profiles. The markers used represent the same reinforcement percentages as those in Fig. 3 and 4. The out of plane (y) direction is shown by a solid line, and the x -direction by dashed line.

As a result, the stress which must be superimposed to ensure zero stress at the newly formed surface is a fourier series the components of which decay exponentially with distance from $y=0$. In order to calculate the net stress within the particle, the resulting equations must be averaged over the width of the particle ($|x| < r_o$), giving rise to the following equations:

$$\langle \sigma_y \rangle = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_o a (1 + k_n y) \exp(-k_n y) \sin^2(k_n r_o)}{2\pi n^2 r} \quad (7a)$$

$$\langle \sigma_x \rangle = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_o a (1 - k_n y) \exp(-k_n y) \sin^2(k_n r_o)}{2\pi n^2 r} \quad (7b)$$

$$\langle \sigma_y \rangle = \sum_{m,n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_o^2 a^2 (1 + k_{mn} y) \exp(-k_{mn} y) \sin^2(k_n r_o) \sin^2(k_m r_o)}{(2\pi m n r)^2} \quad (8a)$$

$$\langle \sigma_x \rangle = \sum_{m,n=1}^{\infty} \frac{A_o^2 (k_n^2 + 2\nu k_m - k_{mn} k_n^2) \exp(-k_{nm} y) \sin^2(k_n r_o) \sin^2(k_m r_o)}{(k_{mn} m n r)^2} \quad (8b)$$

for fibres and particles respectively, with $k_{nm} = 2\pi \sqrt{(n^2 + m^2)}/a$. The stress profiles are shown in Fig. 4 alongside the FE results for the 5% composite. The results clearly show that the averaged series solution is in much better agreement than the simple method with the experimental results, although the rate of build up of the normal state is still slightly underestimated. It should be remembered that the approach is rather simplistic; it assumes that a surface force can be applied to a elastically homogeneous cross-section containing a stress profiles equivalent to that caused by an array of particles (fibres) spacing a . In common with the approach of Hanabusa et al. [5], the area fraction of particles (fibres) on the newly

created free surface is much greater than the volume fraction of reinforcement because of the periodic nature of the array. Consequently, although the stress is balanced over the cross-section, the phase stresses are quite different from if the section contained a fraction of reinforcing particles equivalent to the composite as a whole, i.e. $f_a = f$. This also has the effect of bringing the particles closer together than would be expected in a randomly distributed composite or for a less special cut through the periodic array. In order to account for this effect, results corresponding to an r_o/a ratio representative of a slice with $f_a = f$ for the 5% composite are also shown in Fig. 4.

While a cubic (square) array of particles (fibres) at this spacing would have a reinforcement content much greater than 5%, this regular arrangement could be thought of as representing a random slice through a randomly distributed system. Besides, the distribution of particles below the free surface ($y=0$) is not actively included in the model anyway. Other simplifications include the fact that the rate of change of stress from a free surface would be affected by the elastic heterogeneity. Nevertheless, the model does capture the effect of reinforcing volume fraction on the rate at which the bulk stress state is reached and is in fairly good agreement with the actual stress values, whilst retaining the simplicity of the approach pioneered by Hanabusa et al. [5]. In common with the FE results the rate of change of stress decreases with increasing volume fraction. The area fraction matched curve shows the greatest rate of change of stress, much greater than the original 5% curve. This is because the model predicts a strong sensitivity to f , only when the ratio r_o/a is small; hence the similarity of the 5, 10, and 20% curves. The FEA data can be seen to lie between the two 5% curves, but can be said to be closer to the new representative area curve, indicating that this approach may have merit, although further work is still needed to confirm this.

Simulation of X-ray $\text{Sin}^2\psi$ Curves

The FE results and the modelling approaches all show that the concept of using the $\text{sin}^2\psi$ technique to measure thermal micro residual stresses for the fibre-like composite in the transverse directions is fundamentally flawed. If the attenuation depth is much smaller than the microstructure of the reinforcement the normal stress state (σ_y) is zero over the sampling volume, but so too is the in-plane stress so that the $\text{sin}^2\psi$ gradient is zero and no stress would be inferred. If on the other hand, the penetration is large the bulk stress state is sampled and since the stresses two transverse directions (σ_x and σ_y) are equal, deep within the bulk, the $\text{sin}^2\psi$ technique would again record zero gradient, incorrectly suggesting a zero transverse stress component. Note however that it is possible to estimate the average axial fibre and matrix stresses (σ_z) since these stresses decrease only slightly as the surface is approached giving a relatively reliable measure of the stress. In this case the gradient would give σ_z under highly attenuating conditions and $\sigma_z - \sigma_y$ if the reinforcement separation is smaller than the penetration depth.

Given that the extended series approach to modelling the stress profiles is a fairly good predictor of the actual stresses evaluated using our 2D FE model, it would seem reasonable to assume that the 3D series solution is an acceptable approximation for the computationally more demanding 3D case for which it is very laborious to construct a model. The 3D series solution profiles are shown in Fig. 6. Here it can be seen that the predicted stress profiles for 5, 10, and 20% are essentially the same, indicating that except at low r_o/a ratios, the stress profile is dependent only upon a , as for Hanabusa's model. In the x-direction, again our

model shows a shift towards the surface with decreasing volume fraction. In both directions, our models show a greater rise in the stress than Hanabusa's model.

Optimised curve fits describing the stress profiles of the type shown in Fig. 6 were defined and used to simulate the $\sin^2\psi$ curves. In each case best fit straight lines have been used to estimate the phase stress results that would arise were biaxiality of stress assumed. The results are summarised in Table 3 for Cu and Cr radiation. Upon comparing the results with the stresses in the bulk it is clear the thermal mismatch stresses are significantly underestimated and, for Cu radiation, are even of the wrong sign relative to the bulk value.

It is believed that the incorrect sign is achieved because the $\sin^2\psi$ shifts upwards from near the triaxial to the biaxial curve as the penetration decreases with increasing ψ angle. This would record as a tensile gradient. This has been observed in the literature previously for X-ray measurements on Al-SiC particulate composites [7], although unexplained. A similar situation has been observed experimentally by the authors, where thermal micro-stresses were being measured. The lower penetration of Cr would tend to increase the level of biaxiality and this may be responsible for the correct sign of the Cr results. The table also shows that as the percentage of reinforcement gets larger the measured stress increases.

Figure 6: Predicted normalised particle stress profiles in the x and y-directions for a 3D arrangement of particles, spacing a. Markers are as in earlier Figs.

Table 3: Predicted stress results for the reinforcement calculated using the $\sin^2\psi$ criteria for the simulated stress profiles. All stresses are in MPa.

	20 μm (Cu radiation)	20 μm (Cr radiation)	Eshelby
5% in cut plane	6.4 \pm 5.7	-19.3 \pm 8.3	-415
5%	14.3 \pm 7.3	-16.0 \pm 8.1	-415
10%	15.6 \pm 6.8	-7.6 \pm 8.0	-398
20%	17.1 \pm 6.3	2.6 \pm 8.3	-360

CONCLUSIONS

- i) The stress in both the matrix and the reinforcement in a metal matrix composite increases to the bulk value at a much greater rate than predicted by Hanabusa et al. [5], and it is not only dependent upon the size of the particle, but also on the spacing.
- ii) The X-ray 'measurements' indicate that in the Al system, the assumption of a biaxial stress over the x-ray sampling volume is invalid. This could give rise to totally unreliable estimates of the microstress fields. Even using Cr radiation, little improvement is seen. It is expected that in other systems where the penetration is much lower, such as titanium metal matrix composites, that the use of these plots becomes much more useful, although further work will be needed before this can be confirmed.

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